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Research and Innovation action (RIA)*

WIMBY

Wind in My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
CMS	Content management system
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
IT	Information Technology
R&D	Research & Development
R&I	Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package
KIP	Key Impact Pathways
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PNG	Portable network graphics
SQL	Structured query language
SEO	Search engine optimisation

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is an update of the D6.1 Communication and Dissemination document submitted in June 2023. It provides an overview of the progress and effectiveness of WIMBY's communication strategy at the 18-month mark. It encompasses a comprehensive review of past events, graphical products developed, and an evaluation of key performance indicators. Additionally, the update identifies deviations and areas for improvement observed as the project has advanced.

Key sections:

- Section 1: this part showcases the evolution and implementation of WIMBY's communication strategy, emphasising engagement with stakeholders and dissemination of project outcomes.
- Section 2: all published and planned communication products, such as infographics, videos, and social media content are listed and reviewed to assess their effectiveness in conveying project messages and engaging the target audience; and an analysis of events, including webinars, conferences, and workshops illustrates the project's visibility and outreach efforts.
- Section 3: an evaluation of KPIs is presented, providing insights into the impact of communication activities, including website traffic, social media engagement, and audience reach; also, an identification of deviations and areas for improvement offers is presented for refining the communication strategy and optimising future outreach efforts.
- Section 4: this section is dedicated to the analysis of the impacts of the communication and communication activities undertaken during the first half of the project.
- Section 5: final remarks, conclusions and next steps.

1. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION OVERVIEW AND STRATEGY

Dissemination and communication activities represented a key part of the WIMBY project over the past 18 months. These efforts aimed to convey information about the project, promote achievements to all interested parties, and raise awareness across multiple communication channels.

The strategy, outlined in the first version of this document (D6.1 – Communication and Dissemination plan (a)), focused on communicating the benefits of WIMBY to end-users, aiming to raise awareness and connect citizens, municipalities, and local communities with industry representatives and technology providers.

Work Package 6 implemented specific strategies and plans with the final goal of bringing EU-funded research and its results to the attention of multiple audiences. Over the past 12 months (from June 2023 to June 2024), these strategies were implemented and adapted following the project's approach, targeting specific groups such as local communities, industry stakeholders, and policymakers.

The different measures aimed to:

1. **Maximise** the project's visibility
2. **Ensure knowledge** sharing and co-evaluation of solutions
3. **Facilitate the adoption** of research outputs, solutions, and recommendations
4. **Raise awareness** and spread knowledge by interacting with citizens and stakeholders
5. **Attract stakeholders** as potential end-users of WIMBY's results to better understand their needs and provide valuable feedback on project goals and objectives.

Dissemination tasks will continue until the end of the project, consistently communicating progress and results, and engaging all target audiences identified. During this first half of the project, these activities were refined and targeted towards key groups, ensuring effective communication and engagement.

1.1 Communication and Dissemination goals

The key role of WP6 is to support the research by interacting with citizens and stakeholders to raise awareness and social acceptance of wind energy (communication) and to communicate milestones, results, and WIMBY's outcomes to ensure their uptake (dissemination) and long-term impact. The success of the dissemination tasks depended on reaching a wide audience of stakeholders, including those in the energy industry, local communities adopting the collaborative and citizen-led approach for wind-farm evaluation, and renewable energy R&D domains interested in increasing social acceptance by integrating citizens' needs.

Depending on the phase of the project and on the stakeholders expected involvement, the communication and dissemination activities' aim is to reach:

1. **Awareness** of WIMBY's activities, providing all the information about the project, promoting its achievements to all interested parties.
2. **Understanding**, by transferring key messages to specific stakeholders and enhancing their comprehension of WIMBY's outcomes.
3. **Engagement**, by interacting with stakeholder communities, especially citizens living in pilot cases, to promote social acceptance and awareness of wind energy processes.
4. **Use** of results, guidelines and tools developed within the WIMBY project, tailored on stakeholders needs.

In the first part of the project (M1-18), our focus was on raising awareness. We shared project results and progress on social media and our website and participated in conferences to promote our early achievements. Now, at the halfway point of the project, we will shift our efforts towards understanding and engagement. The aim is to engage with the local communities from the different pilot sites and target stakeholder groups, conduct workshops, and gather needs and concerns regarding wind power and wind farms and feedback on project outputs.

1.2 Target audience

In the first version of this document [D6.1 - Communication and Dissemination Plan \(a\)](#), WIMBY's target audiences has been outlined. Four main clusters were identified:

- 1. Institutions, Decision Makers, and Policymakers**
- 2. Research and Innovation Communities**
- 3. Representatives:**
 - a. Main Industry and Manufacturers
 - b. Local Institutions and Entities (public and private)
 - c. Wind-Power Market Related SMEs, Developers, Practitioners, and Public/Semi-Public Companies
- 4. Citizens, Local Communities, and Potential Consumers**

Additionally, in collaboration with the consortium, under WP5 partners identified and defined three specific target groups of users who might be particularly interested in utilising the WIMBY platform and all related scientific results. These target groups are:

- **Interested audiences** – individuals and interested communities seeking knowledge and support in the preliminary evaluation of positive and negative impacts.
- **Specialised users** – researchers, consultants, employees and professionals in the renewable wind energy domain as a supporting tool for preliminary analyses and content exploration.
- **Education representatives** – teachers in secondary schools and university, to use it as an educational support promoting knowledge on energy related issues and their impacts, especially wind power.

More information on how such target audiences have been involved in co-creation and user testing sessions is available in D5.1 Wimby interactive map and general forum, submitted also on M18.

1.3 Communication and Dissemination approach

The WIMBY Communication and Dissemination plan aims to identify the most appropriate methods for each category of stakeholder. In the previous version of the document (D6.1a), the main project goals and target audiences were outlined. The strategy planned at M6 (June 2023) has been

a key element to achieve target KPIs. The main steps in the WIMBY communication and dissemination strategy determined at the beginning of the project were:

- Analysing the needs and interests of the main stakeholder clusters and identifying the intended reactions
- Defining the content to promote related to project findings
- Implementing dissemination activities based on the project's status and target audience, and evaluating the project's progress and current needs
- Implementing a dynamic stakeholder engagement strategy, as outlined in the Grant Agreement (Wimby, 2023). All partners contributed to the development of the plan to ensure continuous interest in the project, participation in co-creation and testing of the WIMBY outputs and adoption of key results.

1.4 Updates and changes to the strategy and approach

The communication and dissemination activity moved in two parallel directions: firstly, increase the understanding of the projects objectives and effectively communicating what is being done and studied; secondly, understanding the needs of stakeholders and producing targeted contents, through the official website and social media channels as through participation in conferences and events and organisation of joint activities with other EU projects and initiatives. Up to date, there have been no major deviations from the initial strategy needed.

Towards the second half of the project, the strategy will focus on promoting the several workshops and planned interactions with local communities, shifting towards dissemination, i.e. the communication of achievements and promotion of tangible results supported by specialised means such as scientific articles and conference presentations.

The next Section 2 will provide a list of completed products and activities developed during the first half of the project.

2. COMMUNICATION MEANS AND ACTIVITIES

The communication of the WIMBY project is a collaborative activity managed by Deep Blue and supported by the entire consortium to ensure effective diffusion of information.

In this section, an update on the completed activities, means, and channels of communication and dissemination that were outlined in D6.1a is provided. Each section details accomplishments, highlight the adjustments made to address project needs, and describe any changes implemented to enhance the communication strategy.

2.1 *Layouted multimedia*

Distribution of branded multimedia products has been crucial for the project identity and recognisability. They were used during organised presentations, public events, forums, and conferences, to reinforce the project messages with visual representation as well. Simultaneously, the same products were uploaded and made accessible via the website, ensuring shareability and readability to the largest audience.

2.1.1 *Dissemination pack*

The dissemination pack is composed of a set of products associated with the project image: the logo, the style guide, and the document templates. It is developed to ensure consistency to the project communication. It is a practical framework shared with all WIMBY consortium and updated throughout the project duration.

The dissemination pack can be consulted in the D6.1 – Communication and Dissemination plan (a) and it contains: the logo in png format (portable network graphics) and vector format, the font styles, the style guide, the word template for deliverables, the power point presentation template and the power point project slide deck. All materials have been made available to partners on the shared repository and updated at need.

2.1.2 Brochures and flyers

One brochure (Figure 1) has been produced to present WIMBY’s objectives, methodology, concept and consortium. The brochures are available for download on the website, both in web and printable version.

Figure 1 - WIMBY brochure (June 2024)

2.1.3 Roll-up and posters

A roll-up (Figure 2) and a project poster (Figure 3) were designed, based on the content used in the brochures. Posters were printed and showcased during public project events and at conferences and workshops.

Figure 2 - WIMBY roll-up (June 2024)

Figure 3 – WIMBY poster (June 2024)

During specific conferences, posters were produced based on the templates provided by the event organisers. This was the case with WIMBY participation in the WIND EUROPE 2024 event in Bilbao (Figure 4).

Figure 4 – WIMBY poster (WIND EUROPE 2024)

2.1.4 Presentations

Laid out presentations were prepared for the participation in conferences, workshops, events, and for the Advisory Board meeting. The presentations for external events contain less textual information and have a predominantly graphical aspect to attract the target audience.

A custom slide-deck (Figure 5) has been prepared and it is organised to be easily updated with tailored content depending on the specific needs of the partner presenting it. This presentation contains fundamental information about the project (objectives, approach, methodology, pilot sites, etc.), which can then be supplemented with more detailed information depending on the specific occasion.

Figure 5 – WIMBY slide deck (June 2024)

2.1.5 Videos

According to the previous deliverable D6.1 – Communication and Dissemination plan (a), WIMBY must produce a video, either in motion graphics or using recorded materials, to showcase the project goals, ambitions, and outcomes. Additionally, WIMBY must create four short video interviews with stakeholders from pilot cases (ranging from citizens to public authorities and entrepreneurs) to collect their feedback on the engagement strategies adopted by WIMBY.

As of the time this document is written (June 2024), the first project video is in production. The consortium opted for a video that combines interviews to the WIMBY's partners and motion graphics scenes. The interviews were conducted during the third General Assembly of the project in Vienna in January 2024, complemented with interviews and footage from the first workshops with local communities (Pantelleria, May 2024). This video will provide an overview of the project, its purpose, and the initial results achieved in the first year and a half of research. It will be used to disseminate information on social media, inform citizens, increase awareness about the project, and during conferences. The video will be published by the end of 2024.

Short interviews with stakeholders from the pilot cases are also planned and will be gradually published. Interviews will be recorded in the stakeholders' native languages and in English, depending on the objective, key message and target audience.

2.2 Communication means and activities

During monthly EB meetings, DBL provides regular updates to all partners related with online activity and related key indicators, such as audiences' visits, country of origin, time spent on the website, and pages raising most interest. Moreover, concerning social media, through LinkedIn analytics several information on followers' role, employment area and seniority are reported. Thanks to such aggregated data, communication and dissemination actions can be adapted to reach out for those target audiences more needed to achieve impact and uptake of results. Noteworthy, despite the obvious high frequency of visitors from partners'

countries, the project WIMBY raises interest beyond European countries and content downloads are steadily growing. In the upcoming months targeted actions focused on consolidating this trend could be explored.

2.2.1 Website and news

The website has been constantly updated and it represents the main dissemination activity channel: news, progresses, events, incoming workshops and any other announcement are issued via its news section. It is also used as a repository of relevant documents, accepted public deliverables, and scientific publications. The website has been updated with news regarding events organised by the project and those in which the project participated, along with the addition of blog posts that are of interest to the audience. All project partners are supporting this task by sharing updates about publications, participation in conferences or new project results. In Table 1 all the articles published in the news section of the website are listed:

Table 1 - WIMBY blogposts

#	Title	Link
1.	Wimby official website is finally online	https://wimby.eu/wimby-official-website-is-finally-online/
2.	Kick off meeting in Brussels 24 January 2023 – short report	https://wimby.eu/kick-off-meeting-in-brussels-24-january-2023-short-report/
3.	Wimby’s partners gather in Vienna for a productive in-person meeting	https://wimby.eu/wimbys-partners-gather-in-vienna-for-a-productive-in-person-meeting/
4.	Wimby releases its first two public documents	https://wimby.eu/wimby-first-two-public-documents/
5.	Wimby’s first press release	https://wimby.eu/wimby-first-press-release/
6.	Wimby joins the fight against co2	https://wimby.eu/wimby-joins-the-fight-against-co2-wind-power/
7.	Designing the Wimby map: how to find your target audience	https://wimby.eu/designing-the-wimby-map-how-to-find-your-target-audience/

8.	Wimby presented at Procida Symposion	https://wimby.eu/wimby-presented-at-procida-symposion/
9.	Global wind workforce report: the growing demand for skilled technicians	https://wimby.eu/global-wind-workforce-report-the-growing-demand-for-skilled-technicians/
10.	What happened during first Advisory Board meeting	https://wimby.eu/what-happened-during-first-advisory-board-meeting/
11.	Abstract submission for EGU General Assembly 2024 now open	https://wimby.eu/abstract-submission-for-egu-general-assembly-2024-now-open/
12.	Supporting and hindering factors that influence social acceptance and commitment to wind energy project	https://wimby.eu/supporting-and-hindering-factors-that-influence-social-acceptance-and-commitment-to-wind-energy-project/
13.	What happened at the General Assembly in Vienna?	https://wimby.eu/what-happened-at-the-general-assembly-in-vienna/
14.	Health and environmental impacts: how wind turbines are responsible?	https://wimby.eu/health-and-environmental-impacts-how-wind-turbines-are-responsible/
15.	Wimby participates in the annual WindEurope conference in Bilbao	https://wimby.eu/wimby-participates-in-the-annual-windeurope-conference-in-bilbao/
16.	Wimby poster at WindEurope 2024	https://wimby.eu/wimby-poster-at-windeurope-2024/
17.	Join Wimby in Pantelleria for the clean energy for EU Islands Forum 2024	https://wimby.eu/join-wimby-in-pantelleria-for-the-clean-energy-for-eu-islands-forum-2024/
18.	Wimby's wind energy workshop at Clean Energy for EU Islands 2024	https://wimby.eu/wimbys-wind-energy-workshop-at-clean-energy-for-eu-islands-2024/
19.	Promoting wind energy development: challenges, strategies and innovations in the EU	https://wimby.eu/promoting-wind-energy-development-challenges-strategies-innovations-in-eu/
20.	Eusew policy session recording available	https://wimby.eu/eusew-policy-session-recording-available/

To enhance the website's visibility on search engines, we've implemented Search Engine Optimization (SEO) functionalities and all blogposts have been copy written for its maximisation. Matomo analytics¹ is adopted to monitor website usage and access, providing valuable navigation insights while protecting visitors' privacy and online security. WIMBY's website is fully compliant with GDPR regulations, utilising trusted services like Iubenda², with Deep Blue acting as data controller. The website privacy policy is continuously updated to comply with the latest EU provisions. Figure 6 and Figure 7 below display the annual (May 2023 – May 2024) website activity, including the number of visits and the geographical locations of the visitors.

Visits Overview

2,368 visits +100% 6,283 pageviews, 4,702 unique pageviews +100%

Figure 6 – Website visits (May 2023 – May 2024)

Figure 7 – Website visitors' locations (May 2023 – May 2024)

¹ <https://matomo.org/>

² <https://www.iubenda.com/en/>

2.2.2 Social networks

For disseminating the project outcomes, the project is using LinkedIn, X and DBL's YouTube channel, as social media. These channels help open discussion around the project topics, not only among an interested and key public but also a more laypeople public, which is a crucial part of the acceptance goal of the project.

- **LINKEDIN** Access link: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/wimby-wind-in-my-backyard/>
- **X** Access link: https://twitter.com/WIMBY_project
- **YouTube:** a channel will be created as soon as the first video is ready for publication

During the first half of the project and until M18, to ensure a successful communication, the project's tone of voice has been friendly and slightly technical, especially when content is directed towards the citizen and the general public. We used clear and concise language to explain technical concepts and ideas, trying to make the message easier to take in. The scientific content has been simplified and made easily understandable, thanks to the blog posts and articles periodically provided by the partners to populate the website. Nevertheless, links to more detailed and technical information have been provided, when available and links with deliverables provided. These efforts have proven highly effective in making communication engaging around the topic of wind energy and have generated considerable interest among the audience.

It has been noticed that X as a social media platform has lost its attractiveness in recent years, limiting the potential for awareness and dissemination of the project's knowledge and results. LinkedIn, on the other hand, has proven more effective for European projects. As a result, the outcomes from LinkedIn are significantly better compared to X. While we will continue to use all platforms without distinction, we will certainly pay special attention to LinkedIn, as it allows for more successful dissemination of the WIMBY project.

The LinkedIn WIMBY account was launched in May 2023. Below the most relevant analytics from May 2023 to May 2024 are reported in Figure 8 and Figure 9.

Metrics

Figure 8 - LinkedIn impressions (May 2023 - May 2024)

Follower highlights

236 Total followers 206 New followers in the last 365 days

Follower metrics

Figure 9 - LinkedIn followers (May 2023 - May 2024)

The WIMBY X account was launched in May 2023. As the platform does not give the possibility to have an annual report of the analytics, but only quarterly, each 6 months we sum the number of impressions (number of times a WIMBY post appeared on the media wall of a member, including both followers and non-followers). Over the first 18 months WIMBY totalised more than 2000 total impressions. In Figure 10 below the impressions analytics from March 2024 to May 2024 are presented.

Your posts earned **400 impressions** over this **91 day** period

Figure 10 – X impressions (March 2024 – May 2024)

2.2.3 Newsletter

The project sends out a bi-annual project e-newsletter to partners, key stakeholders, specific audiences and interested contacts who have subscribed to the form on the website. The newsletter’s aim is to keep the audience interested and informed about activities and results, public deliverables presentation, project progression, publications, with insights, useful links, and relevant contents related to the wind energy domain in Europe.

The first WIMBY newsletter was sent out only in February 2024 to more than 80 addresses. The decision to skip the first year was related to the low number of subscribers and the fact that a press-release was already sent out in seven different languages across Europe through a standard campaign towards press agencies. Two additional newsletter items are planned in the following 12 months: one by July 2024 and another around December 2024 and January 2025, depending on relevant project updates.

2.2.4 Press releases

The first press release was sent out in May 2023, five months after the project kicked-off³. This press release introduced the project, its objectives, methodology, the consortium, and included a quote from the scientific coordinator. We translated the press release into the different partners' languages, producing seven versions in total: English, French, Portuguese, Italian, German, Norwegian, and Danish. Then, the press release news was published on social media and the website, where all seven versions are available for download. Additionally, the press release was sent to over 100 international press contacts. The media coverage was satisfying, with 18 among partners' and online agencies who reported the news of the WIMBY's launch. Below, in Table 2, a list of online references is presented:

Table 2 – WIMBY references online

Date	Link
01/01/2023	https://www.vubtechtransfer.be/wimby
01/06/2023	https://www.energiamercato.it/notizie/aziende-sostenibili/horizon-europe-wimby
02/06/2023	https://www.lamiafinanza.it/2023/06/horizon-europe-wimby-il-progetto-per-rafforzare-il-settore-eolico-in-europa/
03/06/2023	https://piemonteeconomy.it/progetto-wimby-per-leolico-in-europa/
04/06/2023	https://iltorinese.it/2023/06/09/wimby-coinvolgere-le-comunita-locali-per-ladozione-dellenergia-eolica-in-europa/
05/06/2023	https://greenreport.it/news/energia/wind-in-my-backyard-coinvolgere-le-comunita-locali-per-favorire-ladozione-dellenergia-eolica-in-europa/
06/06/2023	https://www.ingenio-web.it/articoli/rinnovabili-wimby-il-progetto-ue-per-promuovere-l-uso-dell-energia-eolica-coinvolgendo-stakeholder-e-comunita-locali/
07/06/2023	https://www.eurekaalert.org/news-releases/992372

³ <https://wimby.eu/resource/1st-wimby-press-release/> – last visit June 2024

08/06/2023	https://www.newswise.com/articles/wimby-engaging-communities-for-the-acceptance-and-adoption-of-wind-energy-in-the-eu
08/06/2023	https://www.unipa.it/WIMBY-coinvolgere-le-comunit-locali-per-favorire-ladozione-dellenergia-eolica-in-Europa/
09/06/2023	https://www.mn.uio.no/its/english/research/projects/wimby/
13/06/2023	https://iiasa.ac.at/news/jun-2023/wimby-engaging-communities-for-acceptance-and-adoption-of-wind-energy-in-eu
13/06/2023	https://www.miragenews.com/eu-launches-wimby-to-promote-wind-energy-1025882/
14/06/2023	https://www.azocleantech.com/news.aspx?newsID=33562
15/06/2023	https://www.ecoticias.com/energias-renovables/dia-global-del-viento-2023
22/06/2023	https://www.apren.pt/en/apren/activities/projectos/wimby/
01/07/2023	https://dblue.it/en/wimby-wind-energy/
02/08/2023	https://boku.ac.at/universitaetsleitung/rektorat/stabsstellen/o-effentlichkeitsarbeit/themen/presseaussendungen/presseaus-sendungen-2023/02082023-boku-windkraftausbau-mit-fokus-auf-nachhaltigkeit-und-akzeptanz

2.2.5 WIMBY General Forum

The WIMBY General Forum is currently an interactive prototype developed on Figma. Its full implementation will follow the WIMBY interactive map development ongoing under T5.3 and in any case not earlier than M24. After user testing sessions, the next step is that of presenting the Forum to the Advisory Board, which next meeting is planned online on M22 (October 2024). This will be possible thanks to the current maturity of the WIMBY platform, which advanced prototype is currently under refinement, in close collaboration among WP5 and WP6 partners involved in the development.

2.2.6 Internal communication

All partners interact regularly, with periodic updates provided during planned General Assemblies and Executive Board meetings. Additional meetings are organised by WP leaders as needed to ensure open exchange within the Consortium. Internal communication is facilitated through a set of project mailing lists, a SharePoint document management system, and the Mattermost platform, which proved to be a significant asset for efficient,

real-time communication. We created various channels on Mattermost dedicated to each WP, with specific sub-channels for discussing specific topics, events, conferences, etc. Figure 11, below, is a screenshot of the welcome channel on Mattermost, containing information on how to use the platform.

Figure 11 – Mattermost welcome channel

2.3 Dissemination activities

The dissemination means and activities described in this section aim to enhance the outreach of project results, making scientific findings a common good and maximizing the project's impact. These activities continue to play a crucial role in reaching wider audiences and ensuring that project outcomes are widely accessible and impactful.

2.3.1 Dissemination towards the Advisory Board

The first Advisory Board meeting was held in October 2023, to gather initial insights and feedback for the research. The meeting began with a project introduction and an ice-breaking activity (a report about the meeting was published on the website⁴). During the WP feedback sessions, each WP leader presented their progress and posed open questions to the AB

⁴ <https://wimby.eu/what-happened-during-first-advisory-board-meeting/>

members. Topics ranged from the articulation of the Web GIS tool and environmental assessment to societal engagement in pilot cases and the mapping of best practices and trade-offs. The AB provided valuable input, particularly on the importance of including natural parks and reserves boundaries, political data, and provide diverse engagement features and options, to meet the diverse needs of each potential user.

The meeting also featured an interactive Miro activity (Figure 12) focused on the General Forum feedback session, collecting participant input on the platform's design, layout and functionality. The meeting successfully gathered useful inputs, guiding the project's next steps.

Figure 12 – Interactive Miro activity during the 1st AB meeting

The second meeting with the AB members will take place in October 2024.

2.3.2 Coordination and networking with other research institutes and EU funded action

To ensure its success and visibility, the WIMBY project has actively collaborated and created synergies with other research institutes, projects

and initiatives within the Horizon Europe Programme framework. Here, in Table 3 the list of WIMBY’s sister projects:

Table 3 – List of R&I projects contacted by WIMBY – Sister projects

List of R&I projects contacted by WIMBY – Sister projects	
JUSTWIND4ALL. Just and effective governance for accelerating wind energy	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101083936 https://justwind4all.eu/
WENDY. Multicriteria analysis of the technical, environmental and social factors triggering the PIMBY principle for Wind technologies	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101084137 https://wendy-project.eu/

Not only the WIMBY Consortium seeks for collaborations to increase awareness and adoption through joint communication and dissemination activities: partners are also proactive in exchanging ideas and share advancements specifically linked to technical tasks. Over the past 18 months, WIMBY has undertaken various activities with its sister projects to enhance mutual growth and contribute to shared research objectives:

- **Meetings:**
 - we established a series of communication and dissemination meetings to establish the foundation for future collaborations, during which we outlined potential joint activities.
 - on the technical front, we held meetings to exchange knowledge and foster collaboration, adopting a common content development board on Trello⁵.
- **Joint articles:** we co-authored two joint articles so far, both available on all three projects’ websites:
 - first joint blogpost: the role of social acceptance and the factors that hinder it, detailing how the three projects address these issues with their unique approaches.

⁵ <https://trello.com>

- second joint blogpost: policy and preliminary regulatory aspects relevant to stakeholders within the wind energy industry.
- **Events:** In partnership with JustWind4All, WIMBY organised a policy session at the European Sustainable Energy Week 2024 event, on the 13th of June in Brussels. Also, in partnership with JustWind4All we organised a special session on Wind Energy at the 6th International Conference on Energy and Environment (ICEE 2024) taking place in Guimarães (Portugal) in June 2024.
- **Horizon Booster:** the WENDY project, which is part of the HB programme, organised a dedicated meeting to discuss communication and dissemination actions. This meeting focused on strategies that sister projects can undertake together to promote key results, as a cluster who address similar topics.
- **Shared research:** With individual partners of JustWind4All, WIMBY is exploring options to include some of their data and models in the interactive map. Moreover, VUB is joining forces with the Autonomous University of Barcelona⁶, to refine their life cycle assessment models. The focus of this collaboration lies on modelling different floating foundation technologies as well as treatment scenarios at the end-of-life of the wind turbines. This exchange is primary among PhDs students working in both projects.

These activities have helped create real synergies, enhanced our research, and facilitated the coordination of dissemination efforts.

2.3.3 Dissemination towards the European Commission

In the upcoming months the institutional EU websites will be contacted to promote the project results at a European level to policy makers, researchers, and a vast variety of experts. The Consortium plans to appear at least twice on one of the following channels:

- Horizon Magazine: the EU research and Innovation Magazine spreading the latest news and features about science and innovative research projects funded by the EU.

⁶ <https://www.uab.cat/web/universitat-autonoma-de-barcelona-1345467954774.html>

- Research and Innovation Success Stories: a collection of the most recent success stories from EU-funded Research & Innovation.
- CORDIS: Multilingual articles and publications that highlight research results, based on an open repository of EU project information.
- BRIDGE or ETIP-SNET Newsletter

2.3.4 Project events and workshops

Public events and workshops are effective means for involving stakeholders and end-users in an effective and successful communication campaign. Feedback from these sessions will be used to improve WIMBY methodology, end users' participation and wind farm social acceptance. Below the list of events to be organised by the project during its three-year life and the update of their status 18 months after the start of the project is provided:

- **12 (twelve) total workshops engaging local citizens and further stakeholders in pilot cases** are planned from M18 to M34 under WP3 in close coordination with WP5 and they will showcase the WIMBY approach and solutions to key stakeholder groups. These workshops have the following characteristics:

1. Open Days: involvement of stakeholders, interest groups, and interested members of the local public in each pilot case to collect qualitative as well as quantitative data through questionnaires and feedback.

- 3 workshops (1 Italian with local population, 2 international with forum participants) and one open day in Pantelleria during the Clean 4 EU Islands Forum 2024, between 12th and 15th of May 2024 – **completed**
- 3 days with 2 workshops on each day in Pantelleria between 16th and 21st of September 2024, including one open day during the visit of the Italian Ministry of Environment and Energy Security – energy transition forum – **planned**
- 3 days with each 2 workshops in Styria from 20–25th of October 2024 – **planned**
- Workshop series in Portugal between January and March 2025 – **to be confirmed**
- Workshop series in Norway from March 2025 – **to be confirmed**

- 2. Detailed pilot site research workshops:** involvement of the local population at a specific pilot site with detailed results from the "open days" will take place in synergy with WP3 workshops described above. Workshops will be organised on different days and timings, to involve different groups such as younger adults, concerned citizens, local politics, and further local stakeholders. Early contacts have been taken with an Italian network of book publishing houses, research institutes and high schools interested in communicating science to the younger generations through the literature students' led prize "Premio Asimov"⁷ and with local organisations interested in renewable energy and citizen participatory processes.
- 3. Closing Workshops:** in a latter phase of the project the involvement of the local population at a specific case study site in foreseen as a half or full day workshop with local stakeholders, where lessons learned are presented and a final MCSA exercise is conducted. This workshop will be planned in a later project phase.

The three first pilot workshops were organised as a test-activity at the Pantelleria pilot site. BOKU, POLITO, and DBL collaborated in organising the event. The three workshop sessions took place on the 13th of May: the first one, in Italian, involved a small group composed of recurrent tourists, one residing citizen, two university students. The second and third workshop, in English, involved Clean4EU Islands forum attendants and some local institutions representatives. Questionnaires were administered to collect feedback and information from the various stakeholders present, and an interactive session was conducted by BOKU. They used a state-of-the-art serious planning game supported with immersive 3D simulations for onshore and offshore wind turbines to transport participants into a virtual reality where they could develop and explore different scenarios for wind power developments in Pantelleria. The high-fidelity reproduction of the island's landscape allowed them to evaluate potential sites and sizes of wind turbines from various perspectives.

⁷ <https://www.premio-asimov.it/commissione-scientifica/>

The workshop aimed to engage stakeholders in a collaborative process to assess the feasibility and implications of wind energy development in Pantelleria. The first workshop was moderated in the local language by DBL and it provided valuable insights on how to involve a local community in evaluating a wind energy development in a familiar area on which they have previous knowledge. A report about the workshop including a photo gallery has been published on the website⁸ and more information on the feedback collected and survey results is included in D5.2, also submitted on M18.

- **3 (three) Advisory Board workshops:** as mentioned in Section 2.3.1, the first AB workshop was held online in October 2023 (M10). The second is planned in October 2024 (M22) and the last one towards the end of the project (around M32).
- **A mid-project public event** will be organised between M22 and M26 to promote project outcomes, instead of by M22 as previously planned. The need of postponing the event emerged to better align with previous pilot site workshop series and avoid overlapping responsibilities and burden on involved partners. Such event will likely be realised either in parallel with a pilot site workshop or as a joint event with other projects. Currently different options are under evaluation.
- **A Final public event** between M32 and M36 is planned.

Partners conducting the workshops must use tailored communication materials and templates. As done for Pantelleria’s first workshops, the graphic products, questionnaires, surveys and all the materials were translated in Italian, which proved to be very useful for obtaining the necessary consent and information from the population without the language barrier. Strategies for anonymisation by design were implemented during the workshop, which shall be considered a best practice by all partners when collecting background information and

⁸<https://wimby.eu/wimbys-wind-energy-workshop-at-clean-energy-for-eu-islands-2024/>

feedback from respondents. More details can be found in D5.2 report submitted on M18.

2.3.5 Third parties' events and conferences

Participating in events increases visibility and helps connect with stakeholders and other experts in the field. Our partners have actively participated in several strategic events to promote WIMBY and disseminate its findings. In Table 4 below a list of events that the consortium attended during the first 18 months of the project is presented:

Table 4 – List of external events and conferences

Date	Event	Target audience	Partner	Peer reviewed
January 2023	JustWind4all Panel participation as invited speaker, Talk and Q&A	Academia, wind power industry, citizens	UU	No
June 2023	Wind Energy Science Conference 2023	Academia	DTU	Yes
September 2023	Poster presentation at Summer School 2023: Energy Technology, Policy and Politics	Academia	ETH	No
September 2023	Poster presentation – XXXII Congresso Annuale della Società Italiana di Ecologia	Academia	UNIPA, POLITO	Yes
September 2023	PROCIDA Symposion – Project presentation	Academia, industry	KIE	Yes
October 2023	RE-Energising Europe (final event of 7 H2020 projects)	Academia, research	VUB	No
November 2023	CINEA Cluster meeting for Wind Energy projects	Research	UU	No
November 2023	Presentation of the WIMBY 3D Participation Environment at the	Professionals	BOKU	No

	Panorama 2023: Digitalisierungsfestival			
December 2023	Presentation at the annual meeting of the British Ecological Society	Academia, research	IIASA	No
March 2024	Wind Europe Conference participation + Poster presentation	Industry, research	DTU, DBL, UU, PSI, BOKU	Yes
April 2024	Presentation at the European Geoscience Union General Assembly	Academia, research	BOKU + UIO + UU	Yes
April 2024	Presentation at the Statistics and Data Science 2024 conference	Academia, research	UNIPA	Yes
June 2024	Presentations and Session organization at the 6 th International Conference on Energy and Environment (ICEE 2024)	research	UU, KIE	Yes
May 2024	Poster and paper presented at the Torque conference in Florence, Italy	Research	DTU	Yes
June 2024	Presentation at the 7th European Congress of Conservation Biology	Academia, research, conservation practitioners and professionals	IIASA, BOKU	No

2.3.0 Scientific articles and papers

During the lifetime of the project, 12 scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals will be released: six during the second year (M13-24) and the remaining six in the third year (M25-36). Also, two articles in general and domain related press and magazines about interesting aspects of WIMBY's

research and results will be published to raise awareness among the general and interested public.

The WIMBY consortium has already published a scientific paper in December 2023 titled "Reviewing accuracy & reproducibility of large-scale wind resource assessments," which appeared in the journal "Advances in Applied Energy". The paper, signed by Russel Mc Kenna from ETH and other authors from FZ Juelich and RWTH Aachen, provides a comprehensive review of methodologies and practices in wind resource assessments based on a systematic analysis of 195 articles. It highlights significant challenges and heterogeneity in global wind potentials and emphasises the importance of data sharing and scientific reproducibility. The publication addresses the inclusion of social and political barriers to wind power development and proposes best practices for future research. The paper is available online and is currently cited by two other articles' authors⁹.

During the conference "Torque conference" in May 2024, DTU presented a poster and paper titled "Need for speed: fast wind farm optimization"¹⁰. The study, part of WIMBY project, focuses on developing a web interface to assist communities in siting wind energy projects across Europe. The research compares two optimisation algorithms to optimise wind farm layouts under computational constraints suitable for web interfaces.

Two further papers are currently under review in lead international peer-reviewed scientific journals: one in the journal "Joule" with contributions of ETH, DTU, UU, BOKU, PSI, KIE, IIASA, UCL, and UiO, titled "System impacts of wind energy developments: key research challenges and opportunities"; and another one in "One Earth" with contributions of BOKU and UU, called "Land-use requirements of solar and wind power".

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adapen.2023.100158> – Last visit June 2024

¹⁰ <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/2767/9/092088/pdf>

3. MONITORING AND KPIS

To ensure the effectiveness of our dissemination strategy, Key Performance Indicators are used to track progress. Below, Table 5 will display their status as of month 18.

Table 5 – KPIS for communication and dissemination activities

WIMBY’s communication and dissemination KPIS	Phase 1 (M1-M12)	Phase 2 (M13-M24)	Phase 3 (M25-M36)	Overall
Public events organised for external audience	0/0	0/1	0/1	0/2
External events attended presenting the project	9/3	6/3	0/3	15/9
Workshops	1/1	3/7	0/7	4/15
Local events/activities organised using the local language	0/0	1/6	0/6	1/12
Number of participants to organised external public events (in person + online)	100+/50	150+/150	0/150	250/350
Ratio of recurring participants to in person events	1%	5%	10%	N/A
Ratio of recurring participants to online events	1%	5%	5%	N/A
Presentations at peer-reviewed international conferences and workshops	3/3	5/4	0/6	8/13
Scientific publication in peer-reviewed journals	1/0	1/6	0/6	2/12
News from the project (blog + social media)	40/10	31/20	0/20	71/50
Articles published on general press/magazines	0/0	0/1	0/1	0/2
Press releases delivered to traditional media	1/1	0/0	0/1	1/2
Number of unique visitors to the website	1055/1200	1311/1000	0/1800	2366/4000
Number of references in other websites	14/10	4/20	0/20	18/50

Number of resources download	103/10	96/10	0/30	199/50
Newsletter subscribers	66/50	16/50	0/100	82/200
Large communication campaigns	1/1	0/0	0/1	1/2
Infographics for different target audience groups	1/1	0/1	0/1	1/3
Project video	0/0	0/1	0/0	0/1
Short video-interviews with pilot cases' stakeholders	0/0	0/2	0/2	0/4

The monitoring of the KPIs has been crucial in understanding the project's progress and in identifying what needed to be implemented and what was truly effective. As visible in the table, we have put significant effort into dissemination through social media and the website, allowing us to reach a broad audience. Currently, we have 306 followers (236 on LinkedIn and 70 on X). Additionally, partners have actively participated in conferences to raise awareness about the project and expand our network.

In the second period, we will focus more on stakeholders' engagement through workshops and events with local communities, as well as developing multimedia materials and videos. These efforts will help us spread the WIMBY message in greater detail.

3.1 KPIs deviations

In a research project and communication strategy, deviations and modifications to the original plans are common and often necessary. These adjustments are typically driven by the dynamic nature of the research, where initial assumptions and plans may need to be re-evaluated as new data and insights are gathered. Additionally, the feedback from stakeholders and the evolving context in which the project operates can necessitate changes to better align with the goals and enhance the overall impact. Also, WIMBY needed some adjustments to its original plans. Below, all deviations from the initially agreed KPIs are listed:

- **Local events/activities organised using the local language:** this KPI has been revised. Previously, in the first deliverable D6.1 – Communication and Dissemination plan (a), there were 4 events

scheduled for the first year, 4 for the second, and 4 for the third. Now, we have adjusted it to 6 in the second year and 6 in the third, as it was not feasible to conduct these meetings without significant results and tools in the first year. Partners agreed that it was too early to conduct these activities when prototypes were not mature enough to be presented and no further tangible results could be easily communicated to external stakeholders.

- **Workshops:** this KPI has been revised upward. In the first deliverable D6.1 – Communication and Dissemination plan (a), 14 workshops were foreseen: 4 in the first year, 5 in the second, and 5 in the third. Currently, the workshops completed, planned and foreseen are 30 in total:
 - a. 3 AB workshops – 1 completed and 2 planned
 - b. 27 pilot sites workshops – 3 workshop sessions and one Open day completed in Pantelleria, 6 workshop sessions planned in Pantelleria, 6 in Styria, 6 in Norway and 6 in Portugal.

The decision was taken jointly by WP3 leaders in coordination with WP5 and WP6 partners, thanks to the first “test” in Pantelleria which resulted in an optimal configuration of activities, logistics and budget. The main ratio was that 3 shorter sessions, possibly combined with an “Open Day” would allow for broader target stakeholder groups engagement, with a relatively small difference in overall effort and no impact on the overall budget.

- **Project video:** since in the first version of the deliverable D6.1 – Communication and Dissemination Plan (a), the first project video was mistakenly foreseen by M12, while the Grant Agreement stated that the video should be produced by the end of the second year, it is hereby postponed to M24 (December 2024), being it a more meaningful deadline to promote the WIMBY ambition methodology and results, namely the WIMBY platform.

4. IMPACT MONITORING

4.1 Key impact pathways

With a new level of ambition to boost the diversity of the impacts of EU research and innovation funding, Horizon Europe incorporates a novel approach to capturing and communicating impacts – Key Impact Pathways (KIP). The objective of this approach is to enable policy makers and the wider public to gain regular insights into the effects and benefits of the Programme over time in relation to European science, economy and the wider society.

In that regard, with Table 6, WIMBY designed a monitoring and evaluation system with the goal to keep track of project achievements contributing towards the KIPs.

Table 6 – Key Impact Pathways

Code	Name	Area	WP6 KPIs	Activity	Result
KIP 1	Creating high quality new knowledge	Scientific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals • Scientific publications in peer-reviewed international conferences & workshops 	Dissemination	<p>1 scientific journal article, 2 scientific journal papers under review</p> <p>15 participations in conferences, 1000+ people reached (overall estimation), 7 proceedings</p>
KIP 2	Fostering the diffusion of knowledge and open science	Scientific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals • Scientific publications in peer- 	Dissemination	All WIMBY papers as well as all the data where we have the rights to redistribute are/will be open access

			<p>reviewed international conferences & workshops</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications as Open Access • Large public events organized for external audiences • External events attended representing the project 		
KIP 3	Addressing Union policy priorities and global challenges through R&I	Societal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications through EC's channels • Workshops (and AB) 	Dissemination	One AB workshop, two workshops with experts and policy makers during Clean4EU Islands Forum 2024. Organisation of a Policy Session during EUSEW 2024.
KIP 4	Delivering benefits and impact through R&I missions	Societal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Liaising activities with EU-funded projects 	Dissemination	Cross-campaigns with 2 sister projects, joint participation to EUSEW 2024, sharing results and joint research tasks.

KIP 5	Strengthening the uptake of R&I in society	Societal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General press/magazine articles published • Press releases delivered to traditional media • References in other websites • Webinars • Workshops • Public Events 	Communication	1 press release in 7 European languages, 12 general press mentions online, 18 references in other websites.
KIP 6	Generating innovation-based growth	Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint and individual exploitation activities 	Exploitation	N/A

5. Conclusions

This deliverable presents an update of the Communication and Dissemination plan D6.2 (a), a thorough document to guide partners and task leader Deep Blue in steering activities throughout the project. The WIMBY project has made significant progress in its dissemination and communication activities, crucial to ensure that the innovative solutions developed within the project are effectively communicated and widely accepted by stakeholders. At month 18 several KPIs have been achieved, with some of them already beyond the expectations for the end of the project. A few KPIs present light deviations and a solid plan to adapt and reach the goals is presented. Concerning the KIPs we have made considerable progress by making use of synergies with policy relevant events and with sister projects. Achievements are shortly summarised below.

- **Engagement with target audiences:** during the first 18 months, the project has successfully engaged with key target audiences, including the scientific community and the citizens. This has been achieved

through active participation in events, conferences, and the organization of in-person workshops.

- **Creation of high-quality dissemination materials:** a range of dissemination materials, including a concept image, posters, brochures, graphical materials, newsletters, etc. have been produced. These materials have been integral in communicating the project's goals and achievements to a broad audience.
- **Internal and external communication:** the project has maintained strong internal communication channels through regular teleconferences and meetings. Externally, we have utilised social media platforms and our website to share updates and results.
- **Collaborative efforts:** WIMBY was committed to collaborating with sister projects. Joint efforts in promoting shared events have helped broaden our network and visibility within the EU research community.

Next steps

As we move into the second half of the project, our focus will shift towards more in-depth engagement with citizens and policy makers. This is crucial for validating our research and ensuring that the solutions developed are practical, effective, and acceptable for the community. Over time more opportunities for dissemination will emerge since most of the scientific results from WP1 and WP2 as well as the tools in WP5 are ready in their first versions and mature enough to be presented and refined through external feedback until the end of the project. Key activities planned for the upcoming period include:

- Work on the official project video and short interviews
- Increasing scientific publications and dissemination opportunities
- Enhanced stakeholder engagement, especially in pilot sites
- Continuous improvement of the dissemination strategy

In conclusion, the WIMBY project is well-positioned to achieve its dissemination, communication, and exploitation objectives and no major deviation are foreseen at this time in the project. Through strategic planning, active engagement, and continuous improvement, we are committed to ensuring that the innovative solutions developed within WIMBY will have a meaningful impact on the energy industry.

